

LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT OF THE TEACHER

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Abstract. *In the article the characteristics of pedagogical management and pedagogical management. Consider the content of managerial competence of the teacher, and organizational expertise of the teacher. The analysis of the status of managerial competence. General and the difference in the content of the management and management by the teacher identified through analysis of the conceptual and terminological phrases “pedagogical management”, “pedagogical leadership”. The definitions of the terms “educational management”, “pedagogical leadership” and as a part of their relationship to the whole. These concepts are responsible for general professional and specific professional skills of the teacher.*

Keywords: *pedagogical management, pedagogical management, professional competence, managerial competence of the teacher, organizational expertise.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрены особенности педагогического менеджмента и педагогической управляющей работы. Рассмотрено содержание управленческой компетентности учителя и организаторской компетентности педагога. Проведен обзор состояния управленческой компетентности. Всеобщее и отличие в наличии менеджмента и начальства со стороны преподавателя выявлено с поддержкой обзора понятийных и терминологических словосочетаний “педагогический менеджмент”, “педагогическое лидерство”. Даны определения терминов “образовательный менеджмент”, “педагогическое лидерство” в составе и их связи с целым. Эти представления отвечают за общевысокопрофессиональные и специфические профессиональные навыки преподавателя.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогический менеджмент, педагогический менеджмент-менеджмент в образовании, профессиональная компетентность, организационная компетентность, управленческая компетентность преподавателя.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada pedagogik menejment va pedagogik menejmentning xususiyatlari. O'qituvchining boshqaruv vakolatlari va o'qituvchining tashkiliy ekspertizasi mazmunini ko'rib chiqing. Boshqaruv vakolati holatini tahlil qilish. Umumiy va o'qituvchi tomonidan boshqaruv va boshqaruv tarkibidagi farq "pedagogik menejment", "pedagogik etakchilik" kontseptual va terminologik iboralarini tahlil qilish orqali aniqlandi. "Ta'limni boshqarish", "pedagogik etakchilik" atamalarining ta'riflari va ularning umuman o'zaro munosabatlarining bir qismi sifatida. Ushbu tushunchalar o'qituvchining umumiy kasbiy va o'ziga xos kasbiy mahorati uchun javobgardir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pedagogik menejment, pedagogik menejment, kasbiy kompetentsiya, o'qituvchining boshqaruv kompetentsiyasi, tashkiliy ekspertiza.*

We are faced with the task of theoretical understanding of the managerial competence of a teacher in order to determine the lines of practical implementation of pedagogical management

and pedagogical management. This problem is indicated by the need to modify pedagogical activity in the aspect of a competence-based approach. The main idea of the study is to describe the content of a teacher's managerial activity as a component of pedagogical activity. The basis for the use of the presented terminological apparatus is the author's dissertation research and scientific and practical material published in the public domain.

The topic of the teacher's managerial competence in various perspectives is revealed in the works of E. M. Zarubina, O. Y. Zaslavskaya, G. N. Serikov, N. V. Nekrasova, V. A. Shevchenko, etc. Based on the analysis of the research data, we came to the following understanding. The managerial competence of a teacher is included in a set of competencies representing professional competence. It is characterized by a dual nature, expressed in the implementation by the teacher of a managerial function based on activities in methodological, creative, professional associations and activities in relation to the student body, as well as the implementation of the management function of the student body in the educational process.

The status of a teacher's managerial competence is determined by the organizational structure of the management of an educational institution and is implemented in practice through pedagogical management in the form of educational activity programs (educational and educational), which are characterized by objective conditions and subjective conditions for the manifestation of a teacher's managerial competence. The basis for the implementation of the teacher's managerial competence is the model of pedagogical management of the functioning and development of the student body, based on general pedagogical, general didactic, specific principles and reflecting the goals, objectives, conditions, organizational mechanism of pedagogical management, published earlier by us in the press. The content of pedagogical management is determined by the goal-setting and design of control actions, as well as their implementation in relation to the student body with the aim of its qualitative change (development). This activity is irreversible, and is ultimately aimed at the development of the student's personality. Consequently, pedagogical management is a manifestation of the teacher's managerial competence [1].

Changing the content of education entails a change in the professional thinking and professional activities of teachers. During the reformation, modernization of education and the definition of strategic directions of educational policy, the use of the phrases "pedagogical leadership", "pedagogical management", "pedagogical management" is found in scientific research and in practice. The conceptual and terminological analysis of "pedagogical management" allowed us to draw the following conclusions. "Pedagogical management" is a specific concept that is used in pedagogical theory is derived from the generic concept of "management". The concept of "pedagogical management" has emergent properties, due to which it can be considered as a type of management, as a level of management and as a form of professional activity. The concept of "pedagogical management" is characterized by the phenomenon of doubleness. On the basis of this provision, the parallel use of the terms "pedagogical management", "pedagogical management", "pedagogical management", "organization of the educational process". The use of terms characterizes professional competence and the level of understanding of the problem.

No	of the basis for comparison	Pedagogical administration	pedagogical management
1	Category of the concept	The level of management of an educational institution	Type of management of an educational institution

2	Status in professional Competence	Special professional skills	General pedagogical skills
3	Place	A component of the educational institution's vertical management system. Management of the structure (student body)	Various aspects of management activities, type of management, component of the organizational management system of the horizontal management of an educational institution
4	Empirical form	Managerial competence of a teacher (special competence)	Organizational professional competence, a component of the organizational structure of management
5	Functions	Analysis, planning, organization, control, regulation	Planning, monitoring, analysis
6	The object of activity	Student body	The educational process of the student
7	The subject of the activity	Self-management of the student body, self-management of teachers	Students' activities
8	Conceptual provisions	Transition from one functional state (pedagogical management) to another (student self-management): redistribution of the functional load of the management of an educational institution	Creating a "developing space" for the purpose of self-development of the student (By K. Y. Vazina)
9	The tools of the activity	The mechanism of pedagogical management	Pedagogical technologies of the educational process organization
10	Management methods	Software-targeted	Software
11	Form of implementation	Management of an institution/organization	Organization of the pedagogical process
12	Performance Indicator	Qualitative changes in the student body, the personality of the student and the teacher.	The degree of education, upbringing and development (According to V.P.Simonov)
13	Evaluation of effectiveness	The level of self-management development of the student body	Compliance of the learning process with the results of education according to the criteria

			of effectiveness
14	Implementation rate	The level of implementation of managerial competence	Organization of the educational process in the institution / organization
15	Resource potential	Forms and types of self-management activities of the teaching staff and the student body	Operational adjustment of methods of education and training

Pedagogical management correlates with the management of an educational institution as its management level, being part of the management system of an educational institution, therefore, this management can be considered as a component of the management system of an educational institution along the management vertical. Pedagogical management is implemented through the process of subject-object relations. In relation to the object of management, pedagogical management is considered as a type of resource provision for the form of self-government of the student body. Pedagogical All management functions of an educational institution are inherent in management, which is determined by the positional definition of the specified process, namely: analysis, planning, organization, control, regulation.

We have identified three perspectives of consideration of pedagogical management in the research of scientists: pedagogical management as a type of management of an educational institution, pedagogical management as a level of management of an educational institution, pedagogical management as a form of management of an educational institution. The system "pedagogical management – a type of management of an educational institution" is characterized by a management structure based on a typical feature of an educational institution. The following dissertation materials serve as an example: N. S. Tolstov, "Scientific and pedagogical fundamentals of general education school management: Theory and practice of improving intra-school control"; N. M. Halimova, "Pedagogical system quality management of primary vocational education in the context of its modernization: on the example of the Republic of Khakassia". The system "pedagogical management – the management level of an educational institution" is considered in the structure of the level of pedagogical activity and the level of professional competence. For example, A.M. Bondarkova, "Pedagogical management of professional self-development of students of technical universities, students studying remotely"; I. V. Kasyanova, "Pedagogical management of foreign language education of future lawyers in the process of professional training"; E. Y. Nikitina, "Theory and practice of preparing future teachers to manage educational differentiation"; L. N. Pavlova, "Pedagogical management of the development of a children's school children's collective". The system of "pedagogical management – a form of management of an educational institution" is considered through the structure of forms of pedagogical activity (forms of pedagogical management and self-government of students, student body, teachers and teaching staff). For example, G. S. Abuzyarova, "The main trends in the development of student self-government in modern educational systems"; Y. S. Bezrodnaya, "The organization of student self-government as a means of forming the social maturity of high school students"; E. E. Slabunova, "Pedagogical conditions of scientific and methodological support for the development of a multidisciplinary lyceum"; S. G. Azariashvili, "Scientific and methodological work of teachers in improving the educational system in a small-scale

environmentcities"; N. V. Senchenko, "Pedagogicalmanagement of the process of self-realizationof students in the educational environment of the university".The research of V. D. Belikovskiy, K. Ya. Vazina, F. I. Gizatulin, A. F. Lebedev, Yu. N. Petrov, E. V. Pichugina, V. P. Simonov, A. G. Sokolov is devoted to pedagogical management, Based on theseworks we have made the following conclusions.

Pedagogical management isa type of management and characterizes various aspects of management activities. Pedagogical management canbe considered as a system of management methods, the essence of which is expressed in the operational adjustment of methods of educationand training through the process of subject-subject relations. Pedagogicalmanagement can also be characterizedas a component of an organizationalmanagement system. The functions of pedagogical management are planning, monitoring,and analysis. Pedagogical management isthe management of the educational processLet's compare pedagogical management and pedagogical management. The results of this work will allowus to consider the content of pedagogicalactivity in the practical implementationof the teacher's managerial competence. Pedagogical management has the status of a special professional skill, becauseit is a highly professional skillthat is implemented only within the framework of an educational institution. It is presented asa component of the management system of an educational institution along the vertical of management (administrative management of an educational institution, pedagogicalmanagement and self-government of teachers andstudents, self-government of the parent community) [2]. In particular, pedagogical management is considered as the management of a student body, which in turnis the management structure of an educationalinstitution. The specificity of managementis determined by the object of pedagogicalmanagement (student body) and the subject of activity (self-management of student body and teachingstaff). The conceptual positionof pedagogical management is as followsthe transition from one functional state (pedagogical management) to another(student self-government), manifested inthe redistribution of the functional load of the subjects of management of an educationalinstitution. Pedagogical managementis carried out on the basis of an organizational mechanism.

Pedagogical management has the status of a general pedagogical skill implemented through organizational and pedagogicalskills (planning the educational process, choosing the optimal means of pedagogical influence and interaction,organizing self-education and self-government, forming a professional orientation of the personality of students)[2]. Pedagogical management represents various aspects of managerial activity, therefore, the object of the teacher's activity are various aspects of the educational process in order to createa "developing space" for the self-development of the student's personality. Pedagogical technologies of the educational process organization are used.These provisions are summarized in the table"Characteristics of pedagogical management and pedagogical management" (Table).

Conclusions. 1. We relate the concept of "pedagogical management" to "pedagogical management" as a whole to a part.2. Pedagogical management is defined as the management of an educational institution vertically at the appropriatelevel, and pedagogical management isdefined horizontally as the management of an educationalinstitution / organization of the appropriate type of management.3. Pedagogical management is determined by the specificity of professional skills, since this managementis inherent only in educational institutions / organizations.4. Pedagogical management is characteristic of pedagogical activity and is implemented in the educational process of an institution / organization; this managementis inherent in the professional activityof a teacher, expressed through general professional skills.5. The content of pedagogical management is

determined by the level of management of the educational institution / organization and the content of the specifics of student management and self-management of the teaching staff.6. The content of pedagogical management is determined by the specific indicator of management and the content of organizational and pedagogical activities within a specific educational institution / organization.7. The practical implementation of the teacher's managerial competence is carried out through the general professional skills of the teacher, carried out in the educational process in the form of pedagogical management and through the specific skills of the teacher, implemented on the basis of the management of an educational institution / organization in the form of pedagogical management.8. Pedagogical management and pedagogical management are different in terms of performance, efficiency assessment, management implementation indicator and the potential of the teacher's activity. These provisions define the dual nature of the teacher's managerial competence, expressed in the dual content of the managerial nature of pedagogical activity and determine the general professional and specific professional skills of the teacher.

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